

Original article

Prevalence, Motivations, and Awareness of Self-Medication Practices Among University Students: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Self-medication with over-the-counter (OTC) drugs is a common global practice, particularly among medical and university students. While it offers convenience for managing minor ailments, inappropriate self-medication carries significant health risks, including adverse drug reactions and antimicrobial resistance. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence, underlying motivations, and awareness regarding non-prescription medication use among students at Rowad Al-Elm Private University in Tripoli, Libya. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between February and April 2025 involving 201 university students. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered Arabic questionnaire that assessed demographic characteristics, medication habits, sources of drug information, and personal awareness of health risks. Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel. The study was predominantly female (92.0%) and aged 18–30 years (96.0%), with 80.6% enrolled in medical specialties. An overwhelming majority (96.0%) reported practicing self-medication. Pain relievers (39.3%) and flu medications (26.0%) were the most commonly used drugs; however, a concerning 13.9% reported using antibiotics without a prescription. The primary motivation for self-medication was reliance on previous experiences (54.2%). Most participants obtained their medication information from pharmacists (41.8%), followed by doctors (28.9%). Notably, despite 72.6% of respondents acknowledging that self-medication poses a health risk, the practice remained highly prevalent. Self-medication is highly prevalent among students at Rowad Al-Elm Private University. The disconnect between the students' awareness of health risks and their actual medication practices highlights the inadequacy of theoretical knowledge alone in preventing irrational drug use. The high reliance on community pharmacists underscores their critical role in guiding safe OTC use. Strategic awareness campaigns, particularly on social media, alongside stricter enforcement of prescription regulations, are urgently needed to curb the misuse of critical medications such as antibiotics.

Keywords: Self-Medication, Over-The-Counter Drugs, Medical Students, Antibiotic Resistance.

Introduction

Self-medication, defined as the selection and use of non-prescription medicines to treat self-recognized illnesses or symptoms, is increasingly recognized as a critical global public health concern [1]. While the World Health Organization (WHO) acknowledges self-care as a vital component of a resilient healthcare system [2], inappropriate self-medication can lead to severe health consequences.

The convenience of over-the-counter (OTC) drugs allows individuals to manage minor ailments independently, yet it simultaneously introduces significant risks, including misdiagnosis, improper dosing, adverse drug reactions, antimicrobial resistance, and the dangerous masking of underlying severe diseases [3].

University students, particularly those enrolled in medical or healthcare-related specialties, represent a demographic highly susceptible to this practice [4]. Enhanced autonomy, easy access to medical information, and a partial or developing understanding of pharmacology often embolden students to bypass professional medical consultation [5, 6].

Factors commonly driving this behavior include prior experience with similar symptoms, the desire to save time and money, and recommendations from peers, family, or community pharmacists [7]. Despite their academic background, considerable knowledge gaps often persist regarding the safe use of OTC medications, the potential for drug interactions, and the long-term dangers of unguided self-medication [8].

While several studies have explored self-medication trends globally, there is a distinct need to assess these behaviors within specific local contexts to tailor effective educational and regulatory interventions. In Libya, community pharmacies are often the most accessible frontline healthcare points, making the dynamics of OTC drug acquisition unique [9]. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the prevalence, underlying motivations, and general awareness regarding over-the-counter self-medication practices among students at Rowad Al-Elm Private University in Tripoli, Libya. By analyzing demographic data, self-assessed medication habits, and sources of drug information, this research seeks to provide foundational

insights necessary for promoting rational and safe drug use among the university population.

Methodology

Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted in Tripoli, Libya, between February and April 2025. Primary data was gathered using a self-administered, paper-based questionnaire provided to participants in Arabic.

Data Collection

The target population for this study comprised students enrolled at Rowad Al-Elm Private University. The primary data collection instrument was a 12-item questionnaire systematically divided into three main sections: demographic characteristics, self-assessment of medication practices, and general awareness and recommendations (Scheme 1).

The demographic section captured the participants' age, gender, academic year, and field of study. The medication assessment section explored habits surrounding the use of over-the-counter (OTC) medications. Specifically, it examined the frequency of non-prescription drug use, the underlying reasons for self-medication, the specific types of drugs consumed, adherence to package instructions, and the occurrence of any adverse side effects. The final section evaluated the students' awareness of the potential health risks associated with self-medication and gathered their personal opinions and recommendations.

Statistical Analysis

Following data collection, all responses were compiled, tabulated, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2010.

Results

A total of 201 participants met the inclusion criteria and completed the study questionnaire. The majority of participants were aged between 18 and 30 years (n=193, 96.0%), and 185 (92.0%) were female.

The results showed that most participants (n=198, 98.5%) had a university education, while only 1.5% had completed postgraduate studies. Of the total participants, 162 (80.6%) were studying a medical specialty, and 39 (19.4%) were not (Table 1).

Table 1: Bio-demographic data of the participants.

Bio-demographic data	No.	%
Gender		
Male	16	8.0%
Female	185	92.0%
Age in years		
Under 18	0	0.0%
18–30	193	96.0%
31–45	8	4.0%
More than 45	0	0.0%

Educational level		
University studies	198	98.5%
Postgraduate studies	3	1.5%
Are you studying in a medical specialty?		
Yes	162	80.6%
No	39	19.4%

Table 2 shows the self-assessment of medication use among the study participants. The questionnaire revealed that almost all participants had used an over-the-counter (OTC) medication (96.0%), while a small percentage had never used them (4.0%). Regarding frequency, participants used medications without consulting a doctor sometimes (38.8%), rarely (32.3%), mostly (26.4%), and a few always used them (2.5%). Approximately 39.3% of participants most often used non-prescription pain relievers, 26.0% used flu and cold medications, 18.0% used nutritional supplements, 13.9% used antibiotics, and a small percentage (2.8%) used other non-prescription medications.

More than half of the users (54.2%) took non-prescription medications based on previous experiences. Additionally, 23.9% took them based on advice from family and friends, 11.9% for other reasons, 8.0% to save time and money, and 2.0% based on information from the internet. Furthermore, the majority believed that using non-prescription medications could pose a health risk (72.6%), while 18.4% did not know, and 9.0% did not believe it posed a risk. Most users obtained their information about medication from a pharmacist (41.8%), followed by a doctor (28.9%), the internet (16.4%), and family/friends (11.0%). A small percentage (2.0%) got their information from other sources.

Table 2: Medication Self-Assessment.

Medication Self-Assessment	No.	%
Have you ever used an over-the-counter medication?		
Yes	193	96.0%
No	8	4.0%
How often do you use medications without consulting a doctor?		
Rarely	65	32.3%
Sometimes	78	38.8%
Mostly	53	26.4%
Always	5	2.5%
What type of over-the-counter medications do you most often use? (Multiple options allowed)		
Pain relievers	142	39.3%
Antibiotics	50	13.9%
Flu and cold medications	94	26.0%
Nutritional supplements	65	18.0%
Other	10	2.8%
Why do you use non-prescription medication?		

Previous experiences	109	54.2%
Advice from family and friends	48	23.9%
Save time/money	16	8.0%
Internet	4	2.0%
Other reasons	24	11.9%
Do you think using non-prescription medications may pose a health risk?		
Yes	146	72.6%
No	18	9.0%
I don't know	37	18.4%
What is your main source of information about medication use?		
The doctor	58	28.9%
Pharmacist	84	41.8%
Internet	33	16.4%
Family/Friends	22	11.0%
Other	4	2.0%

Table 3 illustrates participants' awareness and recommendations. Almost all participants (99.0%) believed there is a need to raise awareness about self-medication, while only 1.0% disagreed. Regarding the best way to raise awareness, 46.3% preferred social media, 23.9% preferred pharmacies, 23.4% preferred awareness campaigns in schools and universities, and 6.5% preferred television programs.

Table 3: Awareness and recommendations

Awareness and recommendations	No.	%
Do you think there is a need to raise awareness about self-medication?		
Yes	199	99.0%
No	2	1.0%
In your opinion, what is the best way to raise awareness?		
Social media	93	46.3%
Awareness campaigns in schools/universities	47	23.4%
TV programs	13	6.5%
Through pharmacies	48	23.9%

Discussion

The findings of this study provide critical insights into the widespread practice of self-medication among university students at Rowad Al-Elm Private University, the majority of whom are enrolled in medical specialties (80.6%). Our results indicate an exceptionally high prevalence of over-the-counter (OTC) self-medication, with 96.0% of the surveyed participants reporting the use of non-prescription medications.

The 96.0% prevalence observed in our cohort is strikingly high but aligns with global trends, indicating that undergraduate medical students are particularly prone to self-medicating. Having a foundational or developing

understanding of pharmacology often creates a heightened sense of confidence in managing minor ailments, frequently leading students to bypass formal medical consultations [10]. This is further supported by our finding that the predominant driver for self-medication was reliance on "previous experiences" (54.2%). While relying on past prescriptions or prior clinical encounters offers convenience and saves time, it inherently carries the risk of incorrect self-diagnosis or the inadequate treatment of evolving diseases [10].

A significant finding in our study is the heavy reliance on pharmacists. When asked about their primary source of information regarding medication use, the largest proportion of participants (41.8%) identified the pharmacist, surpassing even physicians (28.9%). The community pharmacist serves as a critical frontline healthcare provider and a primary consultant for self-care in the community [13]. Given that students actively seek advice from pharmacies, pharmacists are uniquely positioned to distinguish between patients who can safely use OTC drugs and those who require immediate referral to a physician [10]. Furthermore, pharmacists are essential in preventing the avoidable adverse consequences of irrational self-medication, such as adverse drug interactions and medication misuse [11].

Perhaps the most concerning data point from our cohort is that 13.9% of the participants reported using antibiotics without a prescription. While the majority favored relatively safe pain relievers (39.3%) and flu medications (26.0%), the unprescribed use of antibiotics among medical students is a severe public health threat. Inappropriate self-medication with antibiotics is a fundamental driver of antimicrobial resistance, which can lead to treatment failures, the masking of serious underlying infections, and an increased risk of severe clinical complications [12].

Interestingly, a clear paradox emerged in our study regarding risk perception. Despite 72.6% of participants acknowledging that using non-prescription medications poses a health risk, the practice remains near-universal. This disconnect between theoretical knowledge and practical behavior emphasizes that simple awareness is insufficient to curb irrational drug use.

An overwhelming 99.0% of participants agreed on the need to raise awareness about the dangers of self-medication, with 46.3% identifying social media as the most effective platform. Consequently, future public health interventions targeting university populations should leverage digital campaigns to address specific risks, particularly the dangers of unprescribed antibiotics. Additionally, stricter regulatory enforcement on community pharmacies dispensing prescription-only medications is highly recommended.

Conclusion

This study highlights an alarmingly high prevalence of self-medication (96.0%) among students at Rowad Al-Elm Private University in Tripoli, Libya. Despite most participants

being medical specialty students who recognize the health risks of non-prescription drug use (72.6%), this awareness fails to translate into safe practices. Reliance on prior clinical experiences and the readily available advice of community pharmacists emerged as the main drivers of self-medication. Analgesics and cold remedies were the most commonly used, yet the unprescribed use of antibiotics by nearly 14% of students represents a serious public health concern, directly fueling antimicrobial resistance. The findings underscore the pivotal role of community pharmacists, suggesting that empowering them to triage and educate patients could mitigate risks. Moreover, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and actual behavior requires targeted digital-first public health campaigns, alongside stricter enforcement of regulations prohibiting the dispensing of prescription-only medications without physician authorization.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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